

Electrical Hazard Prevention Program at a Water and Wastewater Utility

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Abstract – Maintenance and operations personnel working in close proximity to the electrical power distribution equipment in the water and wastewater facilities may be subject to arc flash events that can cause injury to staff and disruption of water and wastewater services to the public. The current safety standard for the East Bay Municipal Utility District (EBMUD) which is the Required Safety Practice (RSP) 1800 references the latest edition of NFPA 70E [1] for electrical safety. The NFPA 70E standard together with IEEE 1584 [2] includes methods for assessing and evaluating arc flash risks in the workplace, and has specific requirements for making risk assessments and selecting control measures (e.g., equipment labeling, 2 seconds vs. 1000 seconds rule, PPE, installation of remote racking devices, adjusting breaker settings, etc.). This paper will discuss the history, affected facilities, budget, resources, task sequence, NFPA 70E recommendations, techniques used in selecting control measures, challenges, and the status of this multi-million dollar electrical hazard prevention program that was started in 2004 at EBMUD.

Index Terms — Required Safety Practice, 1000 seconds rule, arc flash risk assessment, digested by microorganisms, biogas, digester gas, 2 seconds rule.

I. INTRODUCTION

EBMUD is a public utility formed under the California's Municipal Utility District (MUD) Act that supplies water and provides wastewater treatment to parts of Alameda and Contra Costa counties in the east of San Francisco Bay Area. Its high-quality water supply system covers 332 square miles and serves 1.4 million customers. Its award-winning wastewater treatment system covers 88 square miles along the San Francisco Bay's eastern shore, protecting the San Francisco Bay, and serves 650,000 customers.

EBMUD owns, maintains, and operates facilities capable of potentially releasing hazardous arc flash energy. As a water and wastewater utility company, EBMUD has to comply with federal, state, and local workplace health and safety regulations to protect its employees and the public. The 2004 California Electrical Code (CEC), which is based on the 2002 National Electrical Code (NEC) [3], requires that electrical equipment shall be labeled for arc flash protection. EBMUD has complied with this regulation and performed incident energy analyses to identify proper levels of personal protective equipment (PPE) for its employees. EBMUD uses power system analysis

software to create a detailed electrical model. The software is used to determine incident energy at various water and wastewater facilities where electrical equipment is installed. It is also used as an engineering tool for determining mitigations at these facilities

II. BACKGROUND

A. Water Facilities

EBMUD's source of water is the Mokelumne River Watershed in the Sierra Nevada Foothills located upstream of Pardee Reservoir near Jackson, California. The water is transported from this 70 billion-gallon reservoir in a system of three closed aqueducts (the Mokelumne Aqueducts). The aqueducts travel 94 miles across the Central Valley and the Sacramento-San Joaquin Delta to the EBMUD's service area. The water system includes a network of reservoirs, aqueducts, treatment plants, pumping plants, and distribution facilities stretching from the Sierra foothills to the east of San Francisco Bay Area. The distribution system includes 155 pumping plants, 170 reservoirs in 122 pressure zones ranging in elevation from sea level to 1,450 feet, and 4,000 miles of water mains. About 40 percent of drinking water is supplied and distributed by pumping water operations [4].

On June 16, 2004, engineering support was requested by the EBMUD's operations staff to assess the arc flash hazard for the high-voltage switchgears and motor control centers at the three raw water (supply) pumping plants facilities prior to the 2004 summer operations. This was requested to comply with the CEC-2004 changes on labeling electrical equipment for arc flash hazard. The three supply pumping plants – namely Walnut Creek, Briones, and Moraga are the largest pumping plants at EBMUD. Walnut Creek Pumping Plants (WCPP) 1, 2, and 3 receives utility power at 115 kV and steps down the voltage to 4,160 volts to distribute power to three 2,000-hp, three 2,500-hp, and four 3,500-hp synchronous pump motors, respectively. Briones Pumping Plant receives utility power at 12 kV and steps down the plant utilization voltage to 4,160 volts for four 800-hp induction vertical pump motors. Moraga Pumping Plant motors are rated at 4,160 volts and consist of one 700-hp, one 1,250-hp, and two 2,000-hp synchronous pump motors.

An example of the EBMUD's initial incident energy analysis results for the WCPP is shown in Table 1. This table was used to summarize the arc flash hazard and PPE requirements for

the specific plant equipment. This table was published in 2005 for WCPP.

TABLE 1
ARC FLASH HAZARD AND PPE REQUIREMENTS

Equipment	Energy (cal/cm ²)	Required PPE Class	Flash Hazard Boundary (feet)
115 kV Outdoor Oil Circuit Breaker	Cannot Quantify	DO NOT WORK ENERGIZED	Cannot Quantify
5 kV Outdoor Switchgear	20	3	55
WCPP 1 & 2 5kV MCC	11	3	29
WCPP 1 & 2 208V Station Service Switchboard	10	3	7
WCPP 3 5 kV MCC	6	2	15
WCPP 3 Station Service	18	3	8

The results revealed a high risk and led to concerns of other EBMUD facilities. As a result, the Electrical Hazard Prevention Program was created to evaluate arc flash that could cause injury to personnel and disruption of water services to the public. EBMUD engineers with the help of Construction & Maintenance electricians identified and prioritized the following facilities requiring arc flash risk assessment:

- 1) 146 Pumping Plants
- 2) 2 Hydroelectric Power Plants (Camanche and Pardee)
- 3) 15 Water Treatment Plants
- 4) 26 Office Buildings
- 5) 9 Non-Potable Pumping Plants
- 6) 3 Service Operations and Maintenance Areas

B. Wastewater Facilities

The Main Wastewater Treatment Plant (MWWTP) collects sewage from homes and businesses in the surrounding communities through the network of city-owned pipes that empty into the collection system where sewage is treated. The MWWTP is also a green factory. Biodegradable wastes in sewage, food scraps and grease from local restaurants, and waste streams from wineries and poultry farms are trucked in, and are mixed together in large tanks and “digested” by microorganisms. The biogas emitted by the microorganisms is captured and used to generate renewable energy to power the MWWTP and exported to the grid.

The MWWTP has two 12kV feeds (redundant) services from the local utility company. The MWWTP major equipment consists of two 12MVA transformers, two 12kV switchgears, three 2.15 MW power generator units (engine-driven generator), one 4.6 MW power generator (gas-fired turbine generator); including for the future, one 5 MW power generator unit, one 600 hp compressor, four 1,250 hp compressors, four

1,000 hp effluent pump motors, six 700 hp Influent pump motors, and more than sixty six 480V motor control centers.

Methane (digester gas) collected from the digesters is used to fuel combustion units (i.e., engines, turbine, and boiler) to generate electricity and heat at the Power Generation Station (PGS). PGS1 building consists of three engine-driven generators. PGS2 building consists of a one gas-fired turbine generator. Total on-site generation capacity is approximately 11 MW. Generated electricity is used to meet on-site demand and surplus is exported to the grid.

The majority of equipment at the MWWTP has incident energy values requiring PPE for category 2 and below.

480V switchgears and motor control centers immediately downstream from transformers generally have the highest incident energy values. This is because a fault on the line side of the 480V main breaker must be cleared by 4,160V fuses on the transformer primary.

The worst conditions occur on low voltage bus for line side faults and where the main breakers are large with short-time delay, I²t function turned on, and high instantaneous settings.

III. HISTORY OF ARC FLASH INCIDENTS

To date, the Water Department has recorded eight arc flash incidents starting in 2004. The majority of these incidents happened during construction, occurring while operating backhoes and cranes. The most expensive (\$4M) and catastrophic incident happened at the Walnut Creek Pumping Plant due to human error and equipment failure.

On February 7, 2011, early in the construction of Specification 2008, an explosion occurred at the Walnut Creek Pumping Plants substation due to reclosing a circuit breaker into a 4,160V cable fault. The explosion destroyed the substation’s 4,160V switchgear, which was scheduled for replacement, and caused extensive damage to underground cables, the substation transformer bank, and other electrical distribution equipment. The key failure modes which led to the catastrophic explosions of the substation were already well-known, had been identified as early as 2004 and 2005 when the initial arc flash risk assessment was performed, and were clearly identified in the March 2007 maintenance test program memorandum and follow-up discussions with EBMUD operations staff. A Case History paper was presented at the 2014 IEEE IAS Electrical Safety Workshop for this incident. The paper was later published in the May/June 2015 of the IEEE Industry Applications Magazine as “Rebuilding after a Disaster – Turning a Bad Situation into an Opportunity to Make Electrical Safety Improvements” [16].

The Wastewater Department recorded two arc flash events since 2001. On February 15, 2005, a reactor (used to limit surge current) on the line side (4,160V) of a substation transformer caused arcing and created a line-to-ground fault due to moisture trapped inside the winding/insulation and trapped dirt built up inside the coils of the reactor.

The reactor was not in use for two years. During the first month when it was energized, a local power monitor measured several disturbances including current and voltage spikes. Within a month the reactor finally “blew” and was severely damaged. The breaker on the line side of the reactor tripped open and caused a power outage to several facilities at the MWWTP. The outage also caused three engine-driven generators connected to the same bus to shut down. The reactor caused a line-to-ground fault and resulted in an arc flash event. The result of the investigation indicated that moisture, dust, and dirt were built up and trapped inside the winding/insulation during the two years that it was de-energized. When energized, arcing occurred.

Fortunately, the substation was built with redundant feed. While the damaged feed was down for repair, the redundant feed was used. The result of this event required EBMUD to install a new reactor, retest all the associated cables, transformer oil, PTs, and CTs. There were no injuries to personnel.

IV. ELECTRICAL HAZARD PREVENTION PROGRAM

A. Objective

The program objective is to perform an arc flash risk assessment of electrical equipment for all water and wastewater facilities to comply with the California Electrical Code on labeling electrical equipment for arc flash hazard.

The overall objective of the program is to have arc flash PPE categories of 2 and under, or provide mitigation methods to reduce the arc flash risks to achieve this objective. Arc flash PPE Category 2 requires a long sleeve shirt, pants, jacket, arc rated face shield, and other protective equipment, which is the daily work wear for EBMUD electricians.

B. Financial and Resources Impact

To perform an arc flash risk assessment, EBMUD has purchased power systems analysis software costing approximately \$40,000. Labor costs involve five engineers working 20% of their time and five electricians working 10% of their time.

The time duration to complete an arc flash risk assessment report is six to ten days and approximately \$10,000 per Water Department facility. EBMUD is averaging 28 facilities annually and spending approximately \$250,000 per year. To date EBMUD has spent \$1.3M evaluating arc flash hazard and issuing equipment labels for the Water Department facilities.

The Wastewater Department is smaller than the Water Department resulting in a smaller budget for the wastewater program. Wastewater Department is averaging approximately \$20,000 per facility and \$50,000 per year. The total arc flash budget is \$500,000. The cost of performing incident energy analysis per facility is more for the Wastewater Department because a typical wastewater facility is much larger than a water pumping plant.

C. Evaluation Steps and Process

The arc flash risk assessment evaluation steps and process are as follows:

1. Request information from the power utility such as distribution system impedance, present systems characteristics that include voltage, positive and zero sequence impedances, 3-phase asymmetric and symmetric short circuit duty, single-line to ground, and existing distribution transformer characteristics. It can take up to 6 months for a response from the request date.
2. Obtain data and electrical survey with EBMUD electricians at each facility. The average duration of this work is one day.
3. Use power system analysis software to input all the data gathered from steps 1 and 2 above (1-2 days).
4. Perform power system software analysis (1-3 days). Analyze the data and run the reports.
5. Evaluate and document the assessment (1-3 days) – Prepare report with summary of field conditions and recommend mitigations formatted well for the electricians to understand the arc flash assessment results.

Completion of these steps involves contributions and feedbacks from different departments at EBMUD as shown in Fig 1.

Fig. 1 Evaluation Steps and Process

Engineers and electricians collect field data on the existing electrical system. The engineers then perform the analysis under different parameters to determine the incident energy levels, and prepare preliminary report with recommendations based on site conditions and feedbacks from participating departments. The models created with the software are very detailed. They include the manufacturers, model numbers, amperage sizes, and settings of all breakers and relays; the transformer sizes and impedances; motor sizes (HP) and types (induction, synchronous, lock-rotor code letter, etc.); cable sizes, types, and lengths; utility information as well as other

sources of on-site power. Operations and Maintenance Support reviews the preliminary report and provides input on the recommended hardware mitigations (e.g., specifying a breaker retrofit kit so the recommended breaker can fit in the existing MCC bucket). The final report and arc flash labels are distributed to Operations and Maintenance Support (Regulatory Compliance) and Maintenance & Construction Department (Electricians).

D. NFPA 70E-2015 Recommendations

Here is a quick review of a few recommendations in the NFPA 70E-2015 edition that EBMUD focuses on in the arc flash program.

1. Section 110.1 (E), Electrical Safety Program Controls – This section requires that an electrical safety program is in place for identifying the procedures for employees exposed to an electrical hazard. EBMUD has safety requirements for low- and high-voltage equipment in accordance with the Required Safety Practice 1800 as mandated by its Regulatory Compliance Office.
2. NFPA 70E-2015 edition tables are used together with the incident energy analysis down to the 480 volt MCC level. For facilities with voltage ratings below 480 volt, use of PPE in accordance with Table 130.7(C)(16) to safely perform the assigned task identified in Table 130.7(C)(15)(A)(a) . It is never assumed that the equipment is properly installed and maintained; EBMUD personnel will always wear the proper PPE when performing any of the activities listed in the table.
3. An arc flash risk assessment shall be performed and shall be updated when major modification or renovation takes place at an EBMUD facility. It shall be reviewed periodically at intervals not to exceed 5 years, to account for changes in the electrical system that could affect the arc flash risk assessment in accordance with Section 130.5(2).
4. EBMUD follows the equipment labeling requirements in accordance with NFPA 70E-2015 edition, Section 130.5 (D).

E. Challenges Along the Way

Utility Company – The system data provided by the power utility company for short circuit calculation and incident energy analysis is a challenge for EBMUD. The utility company has a generic disclaimer stating that their electric systems are dynamic, and due to its many variables, a range of impedances are recommended for an arc flash risk assessment.

For example, the utility company recommends using the following system impedance; maximum: 500 MVA; minimum 4.5 MVA; and maximum X/R ratio: 40. However, the present available fault currents and system impedances are also provided. EBMUD uses the present available fault currents and

system impedances and updates the results every 5 years since the power to EBMUD facilities is relatively stable.

The utility company also provides a range of transformer impedance values similar to what is shown in Table 2. The design or tested impedance of the transformer is recorded on the transformer nameplate. To get the exact impedance would require EBMUD to pay the utility company to shut down the transformer, which may impact neighboring customers. Shutdown coordination with the utility company is also challenging if the troubleman is not available to be on site at the appointed time. The troubleman may have other priorities responding to emergencies restoring power to the public. EBMUD worked around this by purchasing a high-power scope to view the transformer impedance and primary protection device nameplate from the ground level, provided the viewing angle is good and the description on the nameplate is not faded.

**TABLE 2
THREE-PHASE PAD-MOUNT TRANSFORMER
IMPEDANCE RANGE**

Transformer kVA	Secondary Voltage	
	208Y/120 or 120/240	
	Minimum	Maximum
45-75	1.4%	3.5%
112.5-225	1.9%	4.5%
300	2.8%	4.5%
500-1000	5.3%	6.2%

Program Software – Power systems analysis software uses steady-state circuit analysis techniques to solve load flow, short circuit, device evaluation, and arc flash risk assessment simulations. It has limited capability to deal accurately with phenomena involving transient behavior, such as decaying components of short circuit currents produced by motors or asymmetry involving DC exponential decay present in AC faults. When considering the impact of rotating AC motor loads (synchronous and induction machines) on the arc flash risk assessment, the software provides an option to reduce the motor short circuit contribution after a user-selectable time delay. When using this option, the software will accumulate incident energy at a constant rate until the time delay has expired. In reality, there is no step change in an arc energy accumulation, and arc energy accumulation will follow the same exponential decay as the transient short-circuit current, integrated over the transient decay time. In spite of the inaccuracy of this approach, it produces conservative results, and we used this option in the arc flash risk assessment with all synchronous motor short-circuit contributions set to zero after 8 cycles (133 ms).

Breaker Replacement in the MCC – When replacing breakers with functionality features that could lower incident energy level, it often poses a challenge for EBMUD. Especially with the older MCCs, replacing breakers require bucket doors to be retrofitted because of physical dimensional constraints.

Budget – Budget appropriation for the program is also a big challenge for EBMUD. As the scope of work increases, recommended mitigations are developed into a separate budget category. To sustain the program and to comply with current codes and standards, the program and project managers have to collaborate with different departments within EBMUD to prioritize the facilities that require immediate arc flash risk assessment revisions.

F. Status of the Program

Fig. 2 Percentage Complete vs. Not Complete

Based on Fig 2, EBMUD still has many facilities that do not have an arc flash assessment completed. For those facilities, the Electricians follow the guidelines in Table 130.7 in the NFPA 70E. EBMUD has been working on this program for more than ten years now and will also be starting to review the arc flash risk assessment evaluations to keep up with the periodic 5-year review period.

Water Department Facilities

1. Completed
 - 101 Pumping Plants
 - 2 Hydroelectric Plants
 - 15 Water Treatment Plants
 - 2 Office Buildings
2. Future
 - 35 Pumping Plants
 - 24 Office Buildings
 - 9 Non Potable Pumping Plants
 - 3 Service Centers

Wastewater Department Facilities

1. Completed
 - 1 Main Wastewater Treatment Plant
 - 14 Pump Stations
 - 9 Wet Weather and Recycled Water Facilities
2. Future
 - Periodic 5 years review

G. Program Improvements

EBMUD continues to make improvements to the arc flash risk assessment process and incorporating them into designs. For arc flash studies using the power system analysis software purchased by EBMUD, the following are standard practice:

1. EBMUD chose to evaluate each facility with maximum arcing duration of both 2 seconds and 1000 seconds. At a maximum arcing duration of 1000 seconds, the protective device is allowed to perform its function in clearing the fault based on its settings and the TCC curve that was created in the power systems analysis software. At a maximum arcing duration of 2 seconds, incident energy will stop building up after 2 seconds even if the protective device does not clear the fault. Based on the NFPA 70E and IEEE 1584, it is expected that a person's reaction speed would take no longer than 2 seconds to leave the arc flash location. Yet there are some sites that have physical constraints where personnel might not be able to escape the arc flash boundary within 2 seconds. Table 3 summarizes the criteria EBMUD has created for labelling based on the maximum arcing duration of 2 seconds.

TABLE 3
CRITERIA FOR LABELLING BASED ON MAX ARCING DURATION OF 2 SECONDS

Equipment Requirements	Equipment (e.g. MCC)
5' of unimpeded path of egress in front of the equipment (e.g., no bends around a pump, no stairs, no ladder, no railing).	[Yes or No]
Panic hardware is installed or exit door opens outwards without the use of hands.	[Yes or No]
Criteria for 2s max arcing duration met?	[Yes or No]

2. Modified labels are also created to include different scenarios in addition to Article 130.5(C) incident energy, arc rating of clothing, PPE, Highest Risk Category, system voltage, arc flash boundary.

Moving forward with future designs – EBMUD and NFPA 70E in the current 2015 edition advocate the design process outlined in ANSI/ASSE Z590.3 [5]. This document establishes a hierarchy of hazard control measures whereby elimination of the hazard has the highest effectiveness and life cycle value. PPE and administrative controls are at the bottom of this hierarchy. Here is a partial list of prevention through design (Ptd) techniques that EBMUD has started implementing.

3. Double Breaker Scheme – A double breaker scheme on the incoming line has means to shut down the facility without exposing Electricians to a dangerous arc flash risk. This scheme does not

remove the dangerous arc flash risk at the line side of the upstream main, but it provides an opportunity for the Electricians to work on the de-energized motor control center.

4. Fast Relaying Scheme on Medium Voltage Equipment – Medium voltage service vacuum circuit breakers and relays are available for medium voltage services which provides better protection.
5. Owning the Distribution Transformer - Owning the distribution transformer and using transformer differential relaying scheme or zone interlocking control [7] and high resistance grounding [8] which will result in lower arc flash risk.
6. Mitigation Program – EBMUD has a mitigation program that helps apply the recommended improvements written in the evaluations. In addition to these recommended improvements, EBMUD Maintenance department is aggressively replacing main breakers with solid state breakers and installing remote operating devices to remove the hazards from the electricians opening or racking the main breakers at the facility.
7. Equipment Specification – Equipment with less hazardous characteristics is specified (e.g., insulated bus, remote control devices, through-the-door racking, infrared sightglass windows).
8. Control Schemes – Control schemes to provide high-speed power system protection are engineered (e.g., transformer differential, bus differential, pilot wire transfer-trip, arc flash light detection, negative sequence overcurrent).
9. Power Control Monitoring (PCM) System – An integrated PCM system is considered to provide power system situational awareness and improved insight into protection scheme performance.
10. Arc Flash Reduction Maintenance Switch (ARMS) – A maintenance switch with electronic device integrated into the 480V switchgear to reduce the fault clearing time. The maintenance switch is turned on only when electricians work on the equipment.

H. Program Successes

EBMUD’s objective is to mitigate the arc flash PPE category below category 2. From the pie chart in Fig. 3, the arc flash PPE category dangerous was 45% before mitigations and was reduced to 34% after mitigations. The mitigations were done to the main breaker. The line side is still dangerous because the utility owned distribution transformers with primary distribution class fuses has too little current flowing to melt it quickly.

Fig. 3 – Program Successes (Water)

Fig. 4 –Program Successes (Wastewater)

I. Lessons Learned

Utility owned distribution transformers rated with primary distribution class fuses protection have high incident energy levels. This occurs most frequently on the secondary side of the transformer when the primary distribution class fuse will not sense the current during a secondary fault.

A lower short-circuit current can lead to higher incident energy levels because some types of protective devices take longer time to trip for lower current.

Large DC Battery systems have high incident energy levels. EBMUD uses IEC Standard 61660-1 [6] in calculating DC short-circuit current and NFPA 70E, Annex D in calculating arcing current and incident energy. IEEE 1584 does not address arc flash hazards in DC systems while NPFA 70E included guidelines for making DC incident energy and arc flash calculations in Annex D of the 2012 version of NPFA 70E. However, the guidelines included simplified calculation methods based on papers presented at the 2007 IEEE Electrical Safety Workshop and the 2009 IEEE Petroleum and Chemical Industry Conference (PCIC).

High- and medium-voltage electrical systems incorporate extensive protective relaying resulting in high-speed clearing fault and will yield low incident energy levels.

V. CONCLUSIONS

EBMUD engineers in the Water Department and Wastewater Department are managed and organized independently. However, both groups adhere to the same requirements including the Required Safety Practice (RSP) 1800, NFPA 70E, and IEEE 1584 to assess and evaluate arc flash hazards in the workplace. EBMUD continues to improve the electrical safety program to provide a safe workplace for the workers. Since both groups adhere to the same EBMUD guidelines and requirements, the Wastewater Department shares similar issues that include cost, schedule, and challenges to implement arc flash mitigation.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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VIII. VITA

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